

Original Research Article

Love, Community, Errantry: Relational Approaches Toward Mathematical Mistakes

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ABSTRACT: In this article we explore ways of approaching what educators and researchers perceive as mistakes that are consistent with views of mathematics that tolerate ambiguity, contradiction, and multiple possible truths. The approaches we describe draw on works within and beyond the field of mathematics education and detail theories from biologist Humberto Maturana, community organizers Bob Moses and Ella Baker, and poet-philosopher Edouard Glissant. These alternative theoretical perspectives are distinctly relational in their approach. They can build on the field's current conceptualizations of pedagogical responses to errors in ways that attend to calls for broadening what it means to do mathematics and be mathematical.

KEYWORDS: mistakes, relationality, opacity, expansive approaches to mathematics, autopoiesis

During the 2023 annual meeting of the American Educational Research Association (AERA), this author team attended a presentation that described a teacher's responses of "It is okay to make mistakes" to students' procedural errors and to student behaviors that did not reflect a growth mindset (Zhan & Louie, 2023). This statement was being used to encourage students, but for one of us, Romina, that encouragement seemed contradictory—first the teacher conjured the students' efforts as a mistake, and then encouraged them to use the moment as a learning opportunity. "But it is a 'mistake'," Romina responded. While unfamiliar with the discursive framings of mistakes in

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mathematics education contexts, she was deeply familiar with overt and covert coloniality in language education and pointed out two intertwining meanings the teacher conveyed: 1) students should accept and feel comfortable making mistakes and 2) students had erred and their mistakes needed correcting.

Romina's reflection caught Melissa and José by surprise. They were astounded by how numb they had become to the refrains surrounding mistakes⁴ in mathematics classrooms. Romina's comment unsettled their perception of the phrase "it is okay to make mistakes" as seemingly harmless. Instead, they began to hear the undertones that had always been there: you have erred, I have caught it, and now I, through my mathematical authority, am willing to absolve you, provided that you improve in the way I am hoping for and maintain the proper attitude. This way of thinking urged us to question how the field of mathematics education often approaches error and to search for alternatives.

Mathematics education scholars have had much to say about mistakes. Whether these are errors addressed by teachers (Alvidrez et al., 2024) or claimed by students (Kalinec Craig, 2017), there is an agreement in our field that mistakes and what we do with them matter. We find promise in the ways scholars have shown that attention to mistakes without intentional shaming is key to supporting student learning (Borasi, 1987; Hiebert et al., 1997; Liu et al., 2022). While we remain concerned that often this tends to mean that students' mistakes are accepted so long as an authority figure is certain that their learning is "progressing," we recognize widespread adoption of a more open stance towards mistakes. Despite this consensus, in our practice as teachers and as researchers, we have experienced a need to explore approaches to mistakes that extend from calls for broader conceptions of what is considered mathematics and who is seen as mathematical (Abreu, 2022; Bullock, 2024; Gutiérrez, 2017; Robinson, et al., 2023). While certain conceptions of mathematics as a set of acquirable skills that progress according to a linear hierarchy may suggest that teachers apprentice students into math, we view mathematics (and language) as a verb, as something people are always doing (Martínez Hinestroza et al., 2023). Crucially, this means that, for us, there is not a neatly defined, closed community of mathematicians, nor is there a neatly defined mathematics (Skovsmose, 2024). As such, we view all classroom community members as full participants in the (re)creation of math and mathematical meaning—regardless of their age or perceived sophistication (Adams Corral & Rodríguez, 2025; Martínez Hinestroza, et al., 2023).

Mathematics classrooms are highly contextualized—influenced by the values, cultures, practices, and needs of the people who come together to identify, make sense of, and solve problems. Mathematics itself is also highly contextualized—shaped by people as much as classrooms are (Robinson et al., 2023; Sumpter & Sumpter, 2024). Our approaches to what we consider to be mistakes are similar—shaped by who and how we are, and who and how we are together. For us, mathematics cannot be fully separated from other approaches to problem-solving or sense-making, and is inherently in relationship with the many ways we move and think through life (Robinson et al., 2023). This also means that it is highly shaped by the values of our society, one indelibly marked by colonial projects and extractive capitalism (Lebrón Ortiz, 2020). Similarly, the act of labeling or naming a mistake, much like the act of naming something or someone as mathematical, is a political act, and care and attention should be given to the practices we have normalized around the recognition and naming of mathematical mistakes (Skovsmose, 2023).

There may, then, be theoretical approaches that go beyond viewing mistakes as resources to achieve ends defined by teachers, or as deficiencies to be remedied in learners. Here we showcase how perspectives from community organizing, poetry, and biology may offer additional

⁴ We use mistakes and errors interchangeably in reflection of the literature and of the common usage of the terms in PK12 classrooms.

ways to define and respond to perceived mistakes. Our purpose is not solely or primarily to suggest pedagogical interventions to mistakes, but to invite scholars to consider alternative conceptualizations of what a mathematical error is and what our conceptualizations say about the meaning of mathematics education.

Common Conceptualizations of Mathematical Errors

Broadly speaking, our field has worked to classify errors (Radatz, 1980; Yang et al., 2011) and identify their causes (De Bock et al., 2002; Elia et al., 2016, Riccomini, 2005); to analyze the impact of teacher responses to errors (Alvidrez et al., 2024; Gardee & Brodie, 2022; Ingram et al., 2013; Liu et al., 2022; Schleppebach et al., 2007) and devise methods to prepare teachers to encounter mistakes (Benecke & Kaiser, 2023; Font et al., 2024). Frequently, these papers regard errors as “deviations from a norm, the definition of which is crucial to distinguish an incorrect from correct statements” (Benecke & Kaiser, 2023, p. 164). In other cases, more than mere deviations, mistakes were considered revelatory and potentially innovative (Borasi, 1987; Bouvier, 1987; Nesher, 1987). This previous research has contributed to the field’s search for effective ways of addressing errors in mathematics classrooms. Yet, questions remain regarding what these previous approaches say about the nature of mathematics.

Considering Alternative Perspectives

For us, learning mathematics is a relational practice—meaning that it happens between and among people, ideas, objects, and spaces (Maheux & Roth, 2011). To help us think of errors in ways that are consistent with relational perspectives, we turn to ideas from the Global South, including from community organizers Ella Baker and Bob Moses, poet-philosopher Edouard Glissant, and biologist and philosopher Humberto Maturana. Each of these theorists points us towards relational ways of thinking that can challenge the traditions of classrooms and of mathematics to create and justify dualities and hierarchies. As we trace connections across these approaches, we suggest possible routes of re-turn for our conception of error in the mathematics classroom.

¿Quiénes somos nosotrxs para juzgar? From questioning errors to questioning authority

Scholars of mathematics education have long considered mistakes as being both fundamental parts of the learning process and necessary to challenge and refine accepted theories (Nesher, 1987). From this perspective, mistakes represent potential lines of inquiry among members of a learning community (Bouvier, 1987; Nesher, 1987). This approach, recognizing any and all community members’ potential to lead the way and challenge what has been held as true, aligns with the perspective of veteran community organizer Bob Moses. Moses, renowned for developing the Algebra Project, attributed much of his knowledge of organizing to the theories and practices of Ella Baker, who he collaborated with during the Civil Rights Movement in the Southern U.S. during the 1960’s (Moses & Cobb, 2001). An approach to mistakes inspired by Moses and Baker calls on a community to come together with curiosity to consider the theories they rely on with an openness to problematizing what has long been accepted. While the field of mathematics education recognizes and celebrates Moses for his commitment to expanding access to mathematics, his and Baker’s theories of organizing are less often recognized for the significant challenges they pose to the field (Gillen, 2014).

In the 1960's, Baker found herself caught in tensions between veteran organizers and youth activists, when veterans considered the daring tactics of the youth to be grave errors. But Baker, a veteran organizer herself, was willing to push herself:

at no position could we confidently raise questions with a procedure that was getting some results... Maybe this was one of the reasons why... I resorted to the questioning procedure. I was not too sure that I had the answer and certainly was not sure that their method was less effective. (Baker, ca. 1960's)

For Baker, these results functioned as the kinds of disruptions that can disprove theories. Her “questioning procedure” allowed for the consideration of how a perceived mistake could lead to new understandings. At the same time, her awareness that there were tactics getting results that went against traditional procedures influenced a stance of curiosity—one that asked questions with a willingness to learn something new, not as a deliberate challenge.

As Baker explains, the sense among elders that young people might be making mistakes challenged her to reflect deeply: “I took the position, which is a basic human position, that if at any time in human existence one has a right to make mistakes, it's while you're young. And the other was that how did I know whether they were making mistakes or not?” (Baker, ca. 1960's).

Where at first, Baker explicitly names the possibility of mistakes or errors, she immediately undercuts her own ability to make that determination with certitude. She points here to the ways her own curiosity allowed for possibilities, that she had not yet seen or even imagined, to have potential to reshape the world in practical and substantial ways.

Crucially, this curiosity came from a reliance on community—from the possibilities that come with all the other worlds that individuals bring to solving shared problems. For Baker, determining that a mistake occurred required careful analysis of outcomes and could not be made individually. In organizing with youth, questioning her own theories, and trying new strategies with them, Baker was pushing her own theory of mistakes—making room for a right to try out new strategies and be open to learning new theories at any age. From this stance, those seen as experts and leaders might question how they know they are identifying a mistake in the learner and not in themselves, their perception, or the broader field (Nesher, 1987).

It is no surprise, then, that Moses proposed a pedagogical approach that extended Baker's theories into mathematics classrooms. In an interview, Moses described observing a student derive a unique measurement procedure to solve a trigonometry problem (NYU Steinhardt, 2012). This procedure was one that mathematicians consulting on the task had not foreseen or even considered possible, but was also likely to support student thinking on later tasks. At the time, the teacher determined the students' idea was unrelated to the task at hand, an error in process. Moses saw this as a lost opportunity, explaining that in these moments where we believe we have identified a mistaken procedure:

it's not exactly what you asked, but it's the idea that students actually have insights which are, in some senses tangential, or even perpendicular to where you're going and, if you can't figure out how to actually use them, then you really do lose what you're trying to gain. (NYU Steinhardt, 2012)

Just as Baker was open to the possibility of worlds not yet imagined, Moses points to the potential pitfalls that come when we are singularly focused on ensuring that students follow our pre-determined known path. When we lose curiosity and trust in our own certainty, we can miss

out on invitations to be surprised⁵. Accordingly, Moses recommended that educators engage in constant “second guessing,” asking themselves “what really has happened here?” (NYU Steinhardt, 2012). This process could mean accepting students' right to their own approaches to problem-solving and acknowledging that despite the position of authority ascribed to educators and mathematicians, who really are we to “know whether they [are] making mistakes or not?” (Baker, ca. 1960's).

Moses' approach to mathematics teaching was shaped by his experiences as a community organizer—from this approach, mathematics teaching and learning are not about reaching one predetermined destination, but about working within communities to recognize our collective power to sense-make, problem solve, and make determinations about what we need and what we value together (Adams Corral, 2021; Moses & Cobb, 2001). Following Baker and Moses, we might interrogate even those answers that appear to be correct (Nesher, 1987), pose doubts in the beliefs of experts, and be open to the possibility of joining students in collective inquiry and decision-making, where the destination is not fully known ahead of time.

In this call to attend to the goals of the community and to engage in inter-generational collaboration, we see the potential to reconsider the locus of mathematical mistakes. We imagine, for example, alternatives to the frequent approach of the teacher or the researcher determining the occurrence of an error and locating it as belonging to or being the responsibility of an individual student. Beyond the obvious pedagogical implications of involving students in assessing the correctness of each other's mathematical ideas, we wonder about what constitutes sufficient evidence to convince us that we are in presence of an error that requires our intervention. What of errors that arise from the use of specific mathematical concepts in situations that seem to call for other approaches, as in Moses' anecdote? What of the potential error in intervening, rather than allowing for the community to negotiate its own conclusions?

As another example, in story problems written to require one correct answer, the context being modeled could often be solved with an intuitive approach or a broad estimation. Consider the following problem: “ $\frac{3}{4}$ cups of detergent are needed for one load of laundry. How many loads of laundry can Mark wash with 5 cups of detergent?” Following Baker's reflections on her work with younger activists, an analysis of errors may not be limited to students' problem-solving strategies and solutions. Instead, an analysis of error could address whether a situation such as the use of laundry detergent needs the mathematical precision often expected of students. A student could provide an estimation or simply suggest flexibly managing how much detergent to use for each load depending on the number of loads needed. This student would be “getting results,” in Baker's words. Rather than attributing mathematical errors to the individual student, typifying these responses as lacking precision or not completing the task, it may be interesting and enlightening to locate the error in the task itself, in the differing expectations that specific members of the classroom community had for the task, and whose expectations had the power to be labeled as correct. Ultimately, we wonder what research would look like that defines mathematical errors not only as students' deviation from standardized procedures but also as the misapplication of particular areas of mathematics for purposes with which the community of learners is not concerned.

Déjate llevar: From a search for errors to an embrace of errantry

Just as we saw with the exploration of errors as having the potential to challenge accepted theories, scholars of mathematics education have argued that there is power in allowing for what we conceive of as errors to launch creative explorations on the nature of mathematics and of

⁵ This language comes directly from the comments provided by our reviewer, Sofia Abreu.

ourselves as mathematicians (Borasi, 1987; Nesher, 1987). Like Baker’s push towards curiosity and Moses’ urging that we second-guess ourselves, there are ways to question mathematics that allow us to (re)consider what we value, what stories we want to tell about our world, and what it might mean to allow ourselves to wander into other ways of doing mathematics (Abreu, 2022; Borasi, 1987; Robinson, et al., 2023). This push, to allow what we might initially see as a mistake to spur reflection, introspection, and reimaginings, holds echoes of theories shared by Caribbean poet-philosopher Edouard Glissant.

Glissant writes of the possibilities that come from embracing errantry as a way of moving through the world in relation with others, and without attachment to predetermined destinations or overly romanticized roots (Glissant, 1997; Glissant & Obrist, 2021). What may be interpreted as an error could instead be a point of difference in values, approach, worldview, or way of being. Rather than seeking to reduce these moments to the label of mistakes, which leave our own assumptions unchecked, Glissant, like Baker, allows space to see what might be revealed in pausing, in listening, in accepting certain unknowabilities.

For Glissant, embracing errantry means letting go of a fixed and pre-determined trajectory. Much like Moses’ suggestion that students can point us in new directions and reveal new approaches, Glissant (1997) considers what he deems an “ontological obsession” (p. 19), as limiting our ability to enjoy and relate. Instead of fixing on what something is (or is not), we might free ourselves to follow a line of thought and see where it leads *us*, together. Echoing Moses’ assertion that the majority of current classrooms are engaged in “sharecropper education” (Moses & Cobb, 2001), Glissant traces the push for productivity and timeliness back to the plantation. When our shared time is not ours to learn and think and dream at our own pace, but instead, carefully meted out alongside the completion of tasks at high levels of pre-determined accuracy, we continue to find ourselves ensnared in colonial traps.

While some might see hesitancy and allowing for spaces of unknowability to be an abdication of an educator’s responsibility, Glissant helps us consider what is possible if we embrace this way of being that he calls *tremblement*, or *trembling thinking*. *Tremblement* is a way of being that:

is neither incertitude nor fear. It is not what paralyzes us. Trembling thinking is the instinctual feeling that we must refuse all categories of fixed and imperial thought. Tremblement is thinking in which we can lose time, lose time searching, in which we can wander and in which we can counter all the systems of terror, domination, and imperialism with the poetics of trembling—it allows us to be in real contact with the world and with the people of the world. (Glissant & Obrist, 2021, p. 140)

Taking on a relational perspective has the potential to allow us the space to imagine mathematics for new purposes and for new worlds (Robinson, et al., 2023)—mathematics that could be used to design and appreciate futures, as opposed to the mathematics of our current world which has succeeded in “designing for no future” (Escobar, 2018, p. 4). This may mean an expansion of possibilities, of truths, and of mathematics, but that must not paralyze us. We may, for example, approach error analysis differently, to not only categorize teachers’ and students’ ways of overcoming what are deemed as incorrect procedures and answers. Alternatively, Glissant’s view can help us look beyond cognitive and situated causes of errors to consider why differences in communicative preferences and embodied affordances are so easily regarded as ‘mistakes.’ What we consider incorrect may not only be an answer or procedure but also the value-laden aesthetics that are constitutive of mathematics themselves.

Take, for example, what is demanded of a student's explanation, using spoken or written language, of how they solved a problem. Often, these explanations ask students to create the illusion of linearity, one step leading to the next. This demand necessarily silences meandering and recursive problem-solving processes. We wonder what Glissant's trembling thinking could look like in mathematical research that does not set a mathematical aesthetic standard as 'universal' and 'value free.' A student's convoluted and seemingly inaccessible explanation or representation of a solution may be a more authentic representation of the simultaneous and connected elements they considered when solving the problem. Rather than focusing on the answer or the process, 'error' analysis could attend to students' aesthetic choices, and teachers' and researcher's engagement with or dismissal of such choices, providing opportunities to contemplate and take in alternative ways of doing mathematics that reflect differing aesthetic values and connections.

Educando: From finding answers to creating relationships

A view of mathematics and mathematics teaching that emphasizes complexity and relationality positions students as scientists, problem-solvers, and knowledge builders (Bouvier, 1987) and recognizes that learning is intricate and transcendental, extending before and beyond any specific encounter (Maturana, 2001). This perspective, where learning cannot be dissected into sequences of expectations, punishments, or rewards, asks teachers to move away from pre-arranged hierarchies of knowledge and people, and from results-oriented pedagogies where mistakes are deviations from expected results.

Mathematics education scholars drawing on Maturana's work highlight the connection between cognition and action, whereby processes of thinking and knowing are inextricable from our own movements, experiences, and interactions, in ways that make all actions valuable in unique ways (Kieren, 2016; Lozano, 2005). This line of work has contributed to a focus on Maturana's attention to the role of observers in deciding what it means to know in mathematics and who is seen as knowledgeable (Davis, 1995; Kieren, 2016; Reid, 2014, 2020). In engaging in relationality in the classroom, Maturana invites us to move beyond known teacher and student interactions mediated by teaching and learning, which historically have constructed a duality between teachers and students, including between observers and observed (Glissant, 1997). As Glissant explains in his troubling of the relations developed via colonialism, "the duality of self-perception (one is citizen or foreigner) has repercussions on one's idea of the Other (one is visitor or one is visited; one goes or stays; one conquers or is conquered)" (p. 17). This, of course, is particularly important when we consider the traditional relations of a classroom—one in which teachers are always being carefully observed by students navigating new authority figures, and one in which students are observed for ranking and sorting. These latter observations can be of the students' accuracy, but also of the attitude they take to their own learning.

Through Humberto Maturana (1978), philosopher and biologist, we understand that within a learning system teachers are both participants and observers, capable of interpreting a mathematical procedure based on the knowledge they accumulated through previous experiences. The teacher and child are both legitimate living beings that interact in learning, transcending their individuality, changing and adapting one another. Living beings, Maturana (1978) asserts, are creative, autonomous entities in continuous self-reproduction in relation to the medium where they exist and interact; changing, but also creating change. As such, a learning system "has no trivial experiences (interactions) because all interactions result in a structural change" (p. 10). This means that our experiences, regardless of their perceived correctness, result in change and through these changes "we create the world in which we live by living it" (Maturana, 1978, p.18). This is what Maturana conceptualizes as *educar*, a process and encounter of change that intertwines knowledge, experiences, values, motivation, and environment.

Educar⁶ is such a biological encounter—a relational, socioemotional and linguistic practice of *love* and *linguaging*, that is, a reciprocal and dynamic encounter that triggers lasting but not absolute changes. Educar, Maturana asserts (1980, 2001), is to move away from human- and more-than-human-relations based on hierarchies, competition, subjugation, and patriarchal understandings to learning as a legitimating individual and social experience where love allows us to accept one another without abandoning our own individuality, autonomy, and identity.

Glissant, Maturana and Baker urge us to accept differences, reject hierarchies, and embrace the possibilities that come from relation, asking:

- How might your way of thinking relate to my own?
- What do those relations suggest about our approaches and about who we are?
- How does making sense of these relations between our ideas drive us down new routes of thinking, being, and doing?

This relational approach is about being willing to question the extent to which our own ways of thinking are shaped by forces that may very well run counter to our goals as educators. This in turn, helps us to relate with and build community among those with whom we are sharing a classroom space, understanding the limitations that are imposed by “imperial thoughts...thoughts of domination, thoughts of a systematic path toward a truth that we’ve posited in advance” (Glissant & Obrist, 2021, p. 141).

Accordingly, in moments when we may not fully understand another’s mathematical process, it may be fruitful to embrace what Glissant calls opacity—the unknowables that can coexist between us, driving our mutual thinking and growth, without requiring anyone to be fully known or reduced. Relation does not require complete knowledge of someone or their ideas, something that may, in fact, be an impossibility: “to feel in solidarity, ...it is not necessary for me to grasp him. It is not necessary to try to become the other (to become other) nor to ‘make’ him in my image” (Glissant, 1997, p. 193). For Maturana, a child’s ability to recognize and value their innate legitimacy, without needing to improve or change themselves to demonstrate their worth, is the goal when educando⁷. A child that experiences life and learning in their own right and legitimacy, “se respeta a sí misma y no se disculpa por lo que hace⁸,” and, as such, may grow to accept and respect other people wholly. A shift in our understanding of the role of the observer (e.g., parent, teacher, researcher) can shape an approach to perceived mistakes with an eye towards complexity, trust in children’s thinking, and the responsibility of love and ethics (Bouvier, 1987; Maturana, 2001). We can allow those we share learning communities with to think in their own way, sharing as they choose, and develop our own ideas as educators without labels that support sorting, tracking, or gap-gazing (Gutiérrez, 2008).

Following Maturana, Glissant, and Baker’s relational perspectives, we wonder what research would look like that focused on a loving approach to errors. By loving, we are not referring to the widespread recommendations for treating students with kindness or using euphemisms when referring to errors. Instead, we imagine students, teachers, and researchers recognizing and accepting embodied and affective responses to mistakes. Determining the occurrence of a mathematical error would, then, not fall solely on an external observer, such as a teacher or a

⁶ Drawing on Maturana’s philosophy, we use the term *educar* in Spanish which communicates an all-encompassing form of teaching and learning that is culturally specific. *Educar* intertwines knowledge, values, relationships, and social responsibility involving the entire society, across institutions, school, parents, family, adults, etc.

⁷ educating

⁸ Respects themselves unapologetically

researcher. This approach could help us delay the impulse to prevent or correct and, instead, sit with a mistake—let it change us. The focus would be less on the cognitive aspect, a topic emphasized in the research discussed above, and more on the relational aspect between error, student, teacher, and researcher.

Instead of deviations from a pre-determined standard, mathematical errors might be recognized as expected visitors who provoke particular emotions, heighten certain intuitions, and encourage specific explorations with others and within ourselves. Errors might elicit discomfort, excitement, amusement, or anger. By postponing the race to fixing mistakes and controlling reactions, research and teaching taking this stance could recognize and empower multiple, sometimes conflicting feelings about errors and the mathematical sensitivities that these emotions may encourage. Accepting each other's mistakes not as precursors of true mathematical statements but as part of ourselves can help expand the process of learning (mathematics) to include mutual acceptance as we are, without contingency.

Discussion

Presently, mathematics education appears to have a deep discomfort with errors—at once, recognizing their inherent role in the learning process, but often assuming that adults can identify errors with certainty (Alvidrez, et al., 2024; Font et al., 2024) and that they are required to work towards the eventual elimination of errors to ensure students' achievement of the standards said to define mathematics learning (Gardee & Brodie, 2022). To a certain extent, we may be particularly drawn to identify, and even conjure, errors because of their potential to promote cultural norms. Within neoliberal societies these might be norms of constant self-improvement and personal responsibility, rooted in a fixation on human 'capital,' (Bradbury, 2019; Vassallo, 2020). What does it mean to repeat refrains that it is "okay to make mistakes," because we can use them to improve ourselves? What might it mean to take the advice of the theorists we discussed above:

- to question our own ability to recognize errors and remain open to new, collectively-derived possibilities with Baker and Moses?
- to embrace wandering while rejecting an attachment to the kinds of categories that feel fixed—right vs. wrong, mathematically beautiful vs. primitive—with Glissant?
- to view the work of educando as an effort to accompany the natural processes of learning and relating with Maturana?

Within a larger colonial project of Western mathematics (Abreu, 2022; Bishop, 1990), we might also look at the possibilities that emerge from being willing to question what it is we are calling mathematics, what we are doing it for, and what it might mean to center relation, possibility, and divergence in mathematics classrooms. In much of the globe, and certainly in the Americas, mathematics classrooms cannot be separated from a larger colonial cosmivision where we classify living and non-living beings, sub-classify the living as humans or sub-human, and privilege the logics of the market—maximizing individual profit, accumulating capital—over all else, claiming extraction as progress, and normalizing violence to achieve those means (Lebrón Ortiz, 2020). For us, mistakes may be just that, mistakes, but they may also be windows into other possible cosmivisions—they may point us towards holes in the dense fabric of colonialism imposed on our communities. What we may see as an error could also point us towards distinct possibilities for what mathematics could be, what mathematics could do, and what mathematics could value outside of this present moment.

Of course, what we have presented are simply options to add to the existing mechanisms teachers and researchers use to make sense of and address what they identify as mistakes. Teachers may choose to analyze and make sense of errors with their classrooms, using errors as a resource (Alvidrez, et al., 2024) or making room for students to claim their own mistakes (Kalinec Craig, 2017); or they may choose to make space for many other possibilities. As language and mathematics education researchers, here we chose to expand the theories that help us (re)define and (re)locate errors in ways that reflect the humanistic and relational aspects we see in mathematics. And it seems to us quite reasonable that young people, less schooled in a certain way of approaching the world, might very well have lessons to teach us if we could pause before being certain we are seeing an error.

We close with a description of an interaction between two five-year-olds that inspired us to think anew about what a mathematical error is, what it is not, and who is involved in deciding. This vignette also gives us a window into how we, as educators, might make space for uncertainty and trembling in relational learning processes (Davis, 1995; Glissant, 1997). In their class, children were counting linking cubes in the middle of their table. After a moment, the children offered two different responses: one claimed there were seven cubes and the other eight. Prompted (by their observer) to decide whether there were seven or eight cubes, the children proceeded to demonstrate to each other how they counted. The first child said the numbers from one to seven as he slid each cube from the center of the table to one side, concluding, again, that there were seven cubes. The second child touched each cube with his finger as he said numbers from one to eight. He, too, maintained his original answer. To our surprise, when asked again whether there were seven or eight cubes, one of the children stated that he understood how his classmate had gotten seven. The other child reciprocated saying that he understood how his classmate had gotten eight. Unbothered, they concluded that maybe there were seven cubes and there were also eight cubes. Satisfied with each other's engagement with the activity, they were not interested in converging to one unique answer, nor did they seek arbitration. Their expectation seemed to be more relational and indeterminate than focused on the individual accomplishment of finding a pre-determined answer. The pressure to reach consensus was external and inconsequential. They did mathematics on their own terms.

This interaction might strike some as troubling, yet we consider it from the perspectives we have shared and with the understanding that this experience does not simply end (Maturana, 2001). These children were interested in exploring one another's conception, but not in identifying one as right and another as wrong. This allowed each to continue on their own pathway of refining their thinking and counting over time. We see this aligning with Maturana's respect for the innate legitimacy of children and their thinking. As these two five-year-olds listen to one another's thinking, we see echoes of Glissant's reminder to co-exist in solidarity, as opposed to trying to fully grasp or even shape people to our image. In similar ways, these children agreed to be comfortable living with multiple truths, regardless of our own well-trained inclinations to determine correctness. In eventually accepting the children's direction for their interaction, their observer demonstrated Baker and Moses' willingness to respect young people's right to make a collective determination about what matters to them at a particular moment, without imposing a premature preoccupation of imagined mathematical doom in their future. For us, this echoes the second-guessing that Moses called for—what might happen if children get to determine the destination for this counting activity? Where might this go over time? What worlds might we build?

Afterword

As we share in our introduction, this paper began with an AERA roundtable that left us chatting for months, years at this point, about the meaning of “it’s okay to make mistakes”. As we turned the phrase over and over in conversation with each other, we found ourselves exploring ways of thinking about mistakes within and beyond the field of mathematics education. As we read within the field, we were struck by a powerful series of essays from the 1980s that seemed to suggest alternative possibilities for approaching mistakes than the ones that had reached peak popularity by the 2020s (you know, the growth mindset “yet”, the neoliberal quest for constant self-improvement). We began to develop a paper that explored parallels between the ideas from the 1980s and those of the philosopher thinkers featured in this piece. When we first submitted our piece, we had no idea what we were in for.

Something about this concept—mistakes—really operates as a kind of third rail or live wire. As we began getting back reviews from other mathematics education journals, we were surprised by the tone of some of the comments we were reading. Many people were downright angry: at the suggestion that mistakes could be approached differently, and also at the idea that there was anything left to say on the topic. We even received comments in all caps—there was an emotional reaction we were eliciting that felt quite extreme.

As we made attempts at revisions through multiple rounds, we began to question the paper. Were we delusional? In our own heads? Should we go to another journal? We sent the paper to a trusted friend who read it and a letter from an editor to see if he found the paper decipherable and worth reading, and to see if he agreed that we should seek a new outlet. He pointed out that the editor whose letter he read, while well meaning, was committed to the idea of one mathematical community, a concept completely at odds with the argument of our paper. He affirmed the value of our contribution, but helped us see that we were likely to never come to a satisfying resolution—we were doing different maths.

José had suggested we consider this journal, where at the very least a keyboard-screaming reviewer would be public, and where there was a commitment to thinking at the margins of the field of mathematics education. If there was one thing we knew after our many rounds of revisions, it is that our ideas were certainly marginalized.

We decided to share our idea with an editor prior to submission. When we first received a response from our editor, David (they/them), we breathed a collective sigh of relief and reaffirmation—the paper had found an (excited and supportive) editor who could see possibilities for many mathematical communities. Their suggestions for additional resources immediately enriched the paper. Preparing the manuscript for submission at JTMME meant going back to the many versions of the paper that had been written and re-written—finding the elements that had been tossed aside by previous reviewers to salvage what was key to us in this piece and also paring back the policing of our ideas imposed by the field.

When Sofía Abreu, whose work in this journal had helped us to push our own thinking about mathematics, read our initial manuscript, we finally had a set of suggestions to strengthen our paper from someone who understood the principles at the core of our work. Her suggestions led to major structural changes to the paper and even made their way in directly. In Spanish, feedback is *retroalimentación*, and *alimentación* is more than a feeding, it is a nourishing relationship. Sofía’s feedback nourished this paper and brought it back to the original intent and excitement with which it was written. As authors we found ourselves gasping at the beauty of this humanizing writing process, the pedagogical, caring, and responsive work of the editorial community. What a gift to experience this process and to be part of this community of thinkers committed to challenging the boundaries of “mathematics education.”

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